

EFFECTIVENESS OF MONETARY POLICY ON PROFITABILITY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN SIERRA LEONE FOR THE PERIOD OF 2012-2018

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to assess the effectiveness of monetary policy on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone for the period of 7 years starting from 2012 to 2018. The profitability of the commercial banks was proxied by Return on Assets and represents the dependent variable, whereas monetary policy rate, Cash reserves ratio, Exchange rate, Inflation rate and Treasury bill rates were used as the independent variables. The secondary data collected were analyzed using Descriptive statistics, Correlation analysis and the multiple linear regressions to test the hypothesis of the study. The study discovered that monetary policy rate, exchange rate and inflation are all having a positive and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks, while cash reserve ratio and Treasury bill rate are negatively related on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone. Since the profitability of the commercial banks anchor on the monetary policies set by the authority, the study therefore recommends that the relevant authority should be extremely cautious when setting monetary policies to achieve macroeconomic objectives.

Keywords: *Monetary Policy, Financial Performance, Profitability*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In most developing countries, the main objectives of macroeconomic policies are to stabilize the economy from both recessionary and boom periods, reduce the rate of poverty and as well as help in stimulating growth in the economy. Sierra Leone like many other developing economies, these objectives are achieved with the help of both fiscal and monetary policies.

Monetary policy is considered as the supply side policy that is used by the authority to control the supply of money and cost of credit in the economy. The macroeconomic objectives of monetary policy are to maintain equilibrium in the balance of payment, price stability and the creation of full employment Abubakarrand Noah (2020); these objectives are however achieved through changes in supply of money, rate of interest and as well as favorable changes in the exchange rate Abubakarrand Noah (2020). While fiscal policy on the other hand, seen as the demand side policy that government uses in order to stimulate the economy and help in achieving its macroeconomic objectives such as maintaining stability in the price level, ensuring full employment, economic stability and economic growth. These objectives are achieved through effective control in government spending and taxation in the economy.

Monetary Policy is among one of the principal economic management tools that governments use to shape economic performance and sound framework Sanusi (2018). Chigbu and Okonwo (2014) defines monetary policy as the deliberate efforts of the government to use changes in money supply, size of credit, cost of credit, and the direction of credit to influence the extent of economic activities to realize desired macroeconomic stability in the economy. The main aim of the monetary authority is to control the supply of money and cost of credit in the market, these aims are achieved through the usage instruments such as the cash reserve requirement, the monetary policy rate, exchange rate, and the open market operation, where government securities are traded, special directives and as well as the use of the prudential guidelines Adeyanju (2021).

For monetary policy to be effective it will depend greatly on how the commercial banks create credit through lending to customers and how they adjust their deposit interest rates to proportional changes in the monetary policy; thus, the variance in this determines whether the monetary policy tools are effective or not. Lamin, (2011). Since the establishment of the Central Bank of Sierra Leone on the 27th March, 1963 and the enactment of the Banking Act in 1964, it enables the central bank to regulate and supervises the activities of all financial institutions within the country.

As stated in the sections 4 and 5 of the Banking Act of Sierra Leone and the revised Banking Act, (2011 and 2019) respectively, it is the responsibility of the Central Bank to formulate, adopt and execute monetary policy and that the monetary policy technical committee (MPTC) within the central bank is responsible to execute such functions under the auspices of the Bank governor. The most important role of this committee is to establish guidelines that will lead to low inflation, high sustainable economic growth and price stability.

However, Commercial Banks as financial intermediaries play an important role in the circulation of money from the surplus unit to the deficit unit and help in managing the risk of future capital flows in a given country. A sound banking system in any country ensures efficient and effective business cycles which can bring about an increment in growth and the standard of living in that particular country. Therefore, the financial performance of commercial banks in terms of profitability is of great importance to a nation.

1.1 Problem Statement

Monetary policy as one of the tools that are used by the government to regulate the economy, plays a vital role in ensuring stability of prices and output in the economy. However, any monetary policy that is successfully implemented requires an active assessment in order to ensure how quickly this policy inject changes in the economy and its effect at large; In order to achieve this, a comprehensive understanding of the policy tools been used by the monetary authority is required Lavally and Nyambe (2019).

Although economic theories and studies from other countries indicate that the economic activity of commercial banks may be largely related to monetary policy, little is known about this situation in Sierra Leone. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the extent to which monetary policy affects the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone.

1.2.1 General Objective

The general objective of the study is to examine the effectiveness of monetary policy on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone.

1.2.2 Specific Objectives

The following are the specific objectives of the study:

- i. To assess the effectiveness of the central bank policy rate on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone
- ii. To determine the effectiveness of cash reserve ratio on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone
- iii. To establish the effectiveness of exchange rate on the profitability of commercial bank in Sierra Leone
- iv. To establish the effectiveness of inflation targeting on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone
- v. To determine the effectiveness of the open market operation on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone

1.3 Research Hypothesis

We will consider the Null Hypothesis in this case; and this state that government monetary policies have no significant relationship on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Monetary Policy

According to John (2017), monetary policy is defined as the tools that are been used globally by the monetary authority to stabilize the economy and address some prevailing economic shocks that arises. The primary objective of the monetary authority in Sierra Leone is to achieve price stability (low and stable fluctuation in the prices of goods and services) help in achieving the government objectives. (Bank of Sierra Leone: Monetary Policy Framework, 2016). Monetary policy is often defined as the instruments at the disposal of the monetary authorities to influence the supply and price of credit/money with the sole aim of achieving price stability Dare and Isaac (2017). Monetary policies, adopted by the Bank of Sierra Leone, have four broad objectives:

- i. **To Maintain a High Level of Employment (Full Employment):** Full employment means a situation whereby everybody who wants job can get one. In order to achieve full employment, there must be sufficient labor, plant and capital at a tolerable capacity to achieve the set goals of national economic policy aimed at combating recession and economic depression
- ii. **To Achieve Price Stability:** Price index stability goal is crucial sense in controlling inflation; it refers to a situation of sustained and rapid increase within the general level of prices. However, the main focus of this objective is to achieve low and stable inflation, and therefore both the economists and layman favor this policy because fluctuations in prices bring uncertainty and instability to the economy.
- iii. **To Maintain Balance of Payment:** Another objective of monetary policy is to maintain equilibrium in the balance of payment. The fundamental objective of the central bank is to ensure that the increase in

money supply is consistent with the objectives of the government for economic growth, inflation and balance of payment.

- iv. **To Achieve Economic Growth:** This means both quantitative and qualitative increase in the total quantity of goods and services produced in the economy annually. Economic growth is defined as the process whereby the capita per income of a country increases over time.

2.2 Theoretical Literature Review

2.2.1 Classicalist and Keynesian Theory

This study is anchored on the Quantity Theory of Money (QTM) which is normally referred to as the theory of the price level, as propounded by the classical economists. However, in contrast to the Keynesian economist, the demand for money theory is referred to as the theory of interest rate, output and employment. The classicalist view on monetary policy is based on the quantity theory of money, which states that an increase or decrease in the amount of money supply would leads to a proportionate Increase or decrease in the stock of money supply. The quantity theory of money is usually discussed in terms of the equation of exchange introduced by Sir Irving Fisher, and is given by the expression

$$MV = PY$$

Where, P represents the price level, and Y denotes the level of current real GDP (or real income). Hence, PY represents current real income; M represents the supply of money over which the central bank has some control; and V represents the velocity of circulation.

The classical economists further based their predictions about full employment condition on a principle referred to as Say's Law. According to Say's Law, "Supply creates its own demand." In other words, within the process of manufacturing output, businesses also create enough income to make sure that each one of the outputs are going to be sold. Prices naturally suit having more or less of something: supply and demand. If there's an excessive amount of something (more supply), prices go down in order that people have more reason to shop for it. If there is an increase in the demand for something (high demand), there might not be enough of it (scarcity); there'll be a competition among the people that want to shop for it, and a few people will accept to pay more to get what they want, as a result of the high demand, prices will go up. The first policy implication is that government intervention isn't needed to take care of economic stability.

On the contrary, the Keynesian theory on the demand for money can be better explained by understanding why money is demanded and as well as the key determinants of the demand for money as proposed by Keynes. According to Keynes, he proposed that money is demanded for three key motives: transactionary motive, precautionary motive and speculative motive. The demand for money is also defined as a function of two variables according to Keynes, that is;

$$M^d = M^d (Y, r)$$

Where; money income is denoted as Y and the rate of interest is denoted as r.

According to the concept of Keynes, the amount of savings by individuals is not dependent on the level of the interest rate. The amount of income saved is dependent on the size of the household's income level. An increase in the amount of income received by a household, the higher the amount of savings would be made by the household. Either the amount of household income does not increase or not decrease, significant changes in the rates of interest will not cause a significant influence towards the amount of savings that will be made by the household.

Keynes further noted that an acceptance of the Say's Law will cause macroeconomic policies redundant. In the classical economist theory, a decision to stop current consumption is as equal as the decision to consume more and more in the future. In relation to this decision, it implies that resources should be diverted to the production of investment goods which will be demanded to provide the flow of future consumption of products. An increase in the amount of income saved it will automatically become an increase in investment expenditure through the adjustment of the rate of interest. The main purpose of Keynes writing the general theory was to provide an academic rejection of the Say's Law, which Malthus over a century had tried and as well as failed to do. According to Keynes theory, production output and full employment are determined by effective demand, and operation of the labor market can't guarantee full employment. The interest rate is ascertained in the money market rather than investment and savings decision.

Keynesians do not believe in a direct relationship between the money supply and the price level, which follows from the classical money supply theory. They reject the idea that the economy is always at or close to real GDP, so the Y in the trade equation is fixed. They also reject the proposition that the movement of money is constant and can cite evidence to support their claim. Keynesians believe in an indirect link between money supply and real GDP. They believe that expansionary monetary policy will increase the supply of borrowable capital through the banking system, which gives lower interest rates at lower interest rates, total expenditure on investment and interest-sensitive consumer goods tends to rise, leading to an increase in real GDP. Therefore, monetary policy can indirectly affect both real GDP and the profitability of investments. However, Keynesians remain skeptical about the effectiveness of monetary policy. They point out that expansion of monetary policies that increase the banking system's reserves should not lead to a multiple expansion of the money supply because banks can simply refuse to lend their excess reserves. Moreover, interest rates fell as a result of the extended monetary policy. There is no need to increase your total investment and consumption expenditure. This is because corporate and household demand for investment and consumer goods may not be as sensitive to lower interest rates. For this reason, Keynesians place less emphasis on the effectiveness of monetary policy and more on the effectiveness of fiscal policy, which they believe has a more direct impact on real GDP and return on investment.

2.2.2 Monetarist Theory.

Since the 1950s, a new view of monetary policy, called monetarism, has emerged that challenges the Keynesian notion that monetary policy is relatively ineffective. Monetarists argue that the demand for money is stable and less sensitive to changes in interest rates. Therefore, expansionary monetary policy only serves to create a surplus of money that households will spend quickly, leading to an increase in aggregate demand. In contrast to classical economists, monetarists accept that the economy cannot always operate at the full employment rate of real GDP. Thus, in the short term, financiers argue that expanded monetary policy can increase real GDP by increasing aggregate demand. But in the long run, when the economy is running at full employment, observers argue that classical quantity theory is still a good relationship between money supply, price levels, and real GDP and investment income. In the long run, monetary policy only causes inflation and does not affect the level of real GDP. Monetarists are particularly concerned about the possibility of abusing monetary policy and destabilizing the price level. They often refer to the Fed's contractionary monetary policy during the Great Depression, a policy they blame for the massive deflation of that period. Monetarists believe that sustained inflation (or deflation) is a purely monetary phenomenon caused by a policy of continuously expanding (or contracting) monetary policy. As a means of combating persistent periods of inflation or deflation, monetarists advocate a fixed rule of money supply. They believe the authorities need to develop monetary policy to maintain steady money growth at a rate equal to real economic growth over time. Therefore, financiers believe that monetary policy should adjust to real GDP growth and return on investment without causing inflation or deflation.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Adeyanjui, O. D (2021) investigated the impact of monetary policy implementation on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, using the descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and the pooled OLS regression model. From the study it was found out that monetary policy rate is positively related with return on equity and money supply is found to be statistically insignificant, while exchange rate and interest rate are found to be negatively related with the return on equity.

Gladys (2018) conducted study on monetary policy and the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya for the period of 4 years starting from 2012 to 2016 for 43 commercial banks using the panel regression model, the diagnostic test was conducted in order to test for stationarity, normality, correlation and the hausman tests. The result from the study concluded that the central bank base rate and the bank size have a negative and insignificant effect on the financial performance of commercial banks, there is a positive and significant effect on the money supply, and finally there is a there is a negative and significant effect of the cash reserve ratio on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya.

Geoffrey (2015) also investigated the effect of monetary policy on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya for the period of 2014-2015. The study makes use of both the descriptive and inferential statistics. The study concluded that Treasury bills have positive and insignificant effect on the financial performance of commercial banks, while the central bank base rate and cash reserve ratio also have negative and insignificant, and finally the bank size have positive and significant effect on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya

Osho and Adelalu (2020) studied the effect of monetary policy and financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2005 to 2019. Using the multiple regression models to estimates the endogenous variables- such as exchange rate, monetary policy rate, and the bank lending rate and the return on assets of the commercial banks was used as the dependent variables. It was found out that the endogenous variables were significantly related to the dependent variables (Return on Assets) and thus concluded that the independent variables have an impact of the financial performance of the quoted deposit money bank as measured by the ROA.

Vijay, Sanjeev and Ly (2020) conducted study on the relationship that exists between monetary policy and the profitability of banks in New Zealand from 2006 to 2016. The generalized method of moments (GMM) was used in analyzing the secondary data. From the result it was revealed that an increase in the short-term rates also leads to a corresponding increase in the profitability of the banks and vice versa. It was also revealed that the capital adequacy ratio of the bank have a positive impacts on banks profitability and non-performing loans ratio and cost to income ratio have a negative impact on the profitability of banks in New Zealand

Mbabazize, Turyareeba and Rumanzi (2020) conducted study on monetary policy and profitability of commercial banks in Uganda for the period of 9 years starting from 2010 to 2018. The secondary data collected and used were analyzed using a dynamic two-step system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) model. The result from the study shows that lending rate have a significant casual effect on the Return on Assets, while rising inflation have a significant and negative casual effect on the Return on Assets of the banks` and treasury bill rate and money supply are insignificant on the profitability of the banks.

Udeh. S. N. (2015) investigates the impact of monetary policy instruments on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria, using the experience of Zenith Bank as a case study for the period of 2005 to 2015. He applied the Pearson product moment correlation and the t-test statistics to analyze the data of the study. From the study it was revealed that the cash reserve ratio, liquidity ratio and the interest rate does not have significant effect on the profit

before tax of Zenith bank, while the minimum rediscount rate on the other hand have a significant impact on the profit before tax of Zenith bank.

Mossadak (2017) conducted study on the transmission of monetary policy in Morocco from policy rate to commercial banks' lending rates for the period of 11 years starting from Q2-2006 to Q4-2016. The secondary data collected were analyzed using A Vector Auto regressive (VAR) model, in which the commercial lending rates instruments are; consumer credit rate, treasury rate, equipment rate and mortgage. The result shows that the variation in the policy rate have a great impacts on the commercial banks rates on the short run than the long run rates.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study adopts the casual research design, in which the target population of the study will consists of the fourteen (14) commercial banks in Sierra Leone. Secondary data will be collected from the Central Bank of Sierra Leone data portal, IMF meta data and the financial stability report from the Central Bank of Sierra Leone and E-view version 8 will be used to analyze the data using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and the pooled ordinary least squares regression model will be used in the study to assess how monetary policy can influences the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone. The use of the descriptive statistics in the study will help to determine whether the series used in the study are normally distributed or not, while the correlation analysis will also help to determine the relationship that exists between the variables used in the study if they are positively or negatively correlated. The scope of the study ranges from 2012 to 2018, this is as a result of changes in some of the monetary policy instruments and it will also serve as a strong period in analyzing the effectiveness of monetary policy on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone.

3.1 Model Specification

The study makes use of the various monetary policy instruments such as monetary policy rate, cash reserve requirements, treasury bills, exchange rate and inflation rate as the independent variables, while the return on assets represent the profitability of the commercial banks as the dependent variable. A multiple linear regression will be used in order to test the hypothesis of the study.

The following is the model specified;

$$ROA = f(MPR, CRR, EXCH, INF, T-BILLS) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

The econometric form of the equation is:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR_{it} + \beta_2 CRR_{it} + \beta_3 EXCH_{it} + \beta_4 INF_{it} + \beta_5 T-BILLS_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where;

Dependent variable:

ROA = Return on Assets

Independent variables:

MPR = Monetary Policy Rate

CRR = Cash Reserve Ratio

EXCH = Exchange Rate

INNIF = Inflation Rate

T-BILLS = Treasury Bill Rate

β_0 = is the Constant or Intercept

$\beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq \beta_5$ = are co-efficient of the study

it = time in period of years

ϵ = Error terms within the variables

3.1.2 Descriptive Statistics / Normality Test

Table 3.1

	ROA	MPR	CRR	EXCH	INF	T_BILLS_RATE
Mean	3.671429	13.07143	11.42857	123.1829	9.79738	8.438571
Median	3.2	11	12	126.76	6.693679	7.95
Maximum	6.1	20	12	142.56	18.21981	22.4
Minimum	2.1	9.5	10.5	101.62	4.645462	2.06
Std. Dev.	1.463687	4.035556	0.731925	13.58457	5.412649	6.828849
Skewness	0.761351	0.721578	-0.42866	-0.239	0.639305	1.26156
Kurtosis	2.085083	2.057115	1.319259	2.161475	1.763384	3.668939
Jarque-Bera	0.92041	0.866755	1.038305	0.27172	0.922851	1.987303
Probability	0.631154	0.648316	0.595025	0.872965	0.630384	0.370222
Sum	25.7	91.5	80	862.28	68.58166	59.07
Sum Sq. Dev.	12.85429	97.71429	3.214286	1107.243	175.7806	279.7991
Observations	7	7	7	7	7	7

From the table above, it was established that aggregate Return on Asset (ROA) had a mean of 3.671429 with a Std. deviation of 1.463687. This is because the Commercial Banks had huge investments in various sector ranging from government securities to tangible assets. It was also evident that the Commercial Banks has channeled enormous resources towards investment in the economy. The result in the table indicates that ROA, MPR and INF mirrors normal skewness and platykurtic (because 2.08, 2.05 and 1.76 are less than 3) and as well as moving towards the long-right tail, whereas CRR and EXCH also mirrors a normal distribution and platykurtic (because 1.31 and 2.16 are less than 3) with a negative skewness indicating that the series has a long-left tail and T_BILLS_RATE on the other hand has a long right tail (positive skewness) and leptokurtic (because 3.66 is greater than 3). The result from the table above further indicates that the probability value of the Jarque-Bera statistics for all the series is greater than 5% (0.05), indicating that all the series in the data are normally distributed.

3.2.3 Correlation Analysis

Table 3.2

Correlation	ROA	MPR	CRR	EXCH	INF
ROA	1.000000				
MPR	0.560493	1.000000			
CRR	0.581176	-0.153156	1.000000		
EXCH	-0.808795	-0.739984	-0.099964	1.000000	
INF	0.885360	0.373717	0.689279	-0.727839	1.000000
T_BILLS_RATE	0.144730	0.872793	-0.476528	-0.477153	0.069196
Probability	ROA	MPR	CRR	EXCH	INF
ROA	-----				
MPR	0.1906	-----			

CRR	0.1712	0.7430	-----		
EXCH	0.0276	0.0572	0.8311	-----	
INF	0.0080	0.4089	0.0867	0.0637	-----
T_BILLS_RATE	0.7569	0.0103	0.2797	0.2789	0.8828

The result in the table above shows that there is a positive and moderate correlation between Return on Assets and the Monetary Policy Rate ($r = 0.560493$, p . value = 0.1906), there is also a positive and moderate correlation that exists between Cash Reserve Ratio and the Return on Assets ($r = 0.581176$, p . value = 0.1712), whereas there is a negative and strong correlation that exists between Exchange Rate and the Return on Asset ($r = -0.808795$, p . value = 0.0276), the result from the table also indicate that there is a positive and strong correlation between Inflation and the Return on Assets ($r = 0.885360$, p . value = 0.0080) and as well as a weak and positive correlation between Treasury bills rate and the Return on Assets ($r = 0.144730$, p . value = 0.7569).

3.3.4 Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 3.3 Hypothesis Testing

Method: Pooled Least Squares
 Date: 02/06/22 Time: 21:47
 Sample: 2012 2018
 Included observations: 7
 Cross-sections included: 6
 Total pool (balanced) observations: 42

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.872339	1.098915	0.793818	0.4325
MPR	0.537728	0.052204	10.30056	0.0000
CRR	-0.772811	0.245097	-3.153085	0.0033
EXCH	0.035677	0.014160	2.519654	0.0163
INF	0.249985	0.038012	6.576403	0.0000
T_BILLS_RATE	-0.265647	0.028316	-9.381647	0.0000
R-squared	0.977648	Mean dependent var		3.671429
Adjusted R-squared	0.974544	S.D. dependent var		1.371537
S.E. of regression	0.218829	Akaike info criterion		-0.069492
Sum squared resid	1.723894	Schwarz criterion		0.178746
Log likelihood	7.459340	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.021497
F-statistic	314.9225	Durbin-Watson stat		3.910103
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The result from the table above shows that MPR have a positive coefficient value of 0.537728 (54%), indicating that the MPR have a positive and significant effect on the Return on Assets (ROA) of the banks. The p. Value of the MPR is 0.0000, indicating that it is statistically significant at p. Value of 5%, whereas the CRR has a negative coefficient value of -0.772811 (-77%), indicating that the CRR have a negative and significant effect on the ROA of the banks. The p. Value of the CRR is 0.0033 which is statistically significant at p. Value of 5%, also the EXCH and INF have a positive coefficient value of 0.035677 (3%) and 0.249985 (25%), with a p. Value of 0.0163 and 0.0000

and as well as statistically significant at 5%. On the other hand, the T_BILLS_RATE have a negative coefficient value of -0.265647 (-27) with a p. Value of 0.0000, indicating that the T_BILLS_RATE have a negative and significant effect on the ROA. From the result in the table, the R-squared value is 0.977648 which mean that about 98% of the predictive power in the dependent variable (ROA) was jointly explained by the independent variables. This implies that dependent variable in Sierra Leone cannot be 100 percent explained by the variables used in this study. The unexplained part of the dependent variable can be attributed to exclusion of very important independent variables that can explain the dependent variable but are outside the scope of this study. The prob value of the F-statistics (0.000000) shows that the overall model is significant at 5%.

4.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The study seeks to assess the effectiveness of monetary policy on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone. From the result in table 3.2, the central bank policy rate has a positive and moderate correlation on the Return on Assets ($r = 0.560493$, p. value = 0.1906), indicating that an increase in the MPR will also leads to a proportionate increase in the ROA. From the result in table 3.3, it shows that MPR have a positive coefficient value of 0.537728 and a p. Value of 0.0000 which is statistically significant at 5% level. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in the study, and concludes that MPR have a positive and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks. Implying that unit increases in the MPR will also a lead to an increase in the ROA by 0.56 times. It was also discovered in table 3.2 that cash reserve ratio has a positive and moderate correlation on the return on assets ($r = 0.581176$, p. value = 0.1712). From the result in table 3.2, it was revealed that CRR has a negative coefficient value of -0.772811 with a p. Value of 0.0033 and statistically significant at p. Value of 5% level. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in the study and concludes that cash reserve ratio has negative and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone. The study further concludes that a unit increase in the cash reserve ratio will lead to a proportionate decrease in the ROA of the banks by 0.77 times.

The result in table 3.2 further revealed that there is a negative and strong correlation that exists between Exchange Rate and the Return on Asset ($r = -0.808795$, p. value = 0.0276), indicating that an increase in the exchange rate will also lead to a decrease in the ROA. The result in table 3.3 also shows that EXCH has a coefficient value of 0.035677 with a p. Value of 0.0163 which is statistically significant at p. Value of 5%. The null hypothesis which indicates that there is no significant relationship between exchange rate on the profitability of commercial banks is rejected in the study based on the significant level. The study therefore concludes that EXCH have a positive and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks in Sierra Leone. implying that a unit increase in the exchange rate will also lead to an increase in the ROA of the commercial banks by 0.037 times.

Also in table 3.2, the study revealed that there is a positive and strong correlation that exists between Inflation and the Return on Assets ($r = 0.885360$, p. value = 0.0080). From the result in table 3.3, it was also revealed that inflation rate has a coefficient value to 0.249985 with a p. Value of 0.0000 and statistically significant at p. Value of 5%. The null hypothesis is rejected in the study and concludes that Inflation rate have a positive and significant effect on the ROA of the commercial banks in Sierra Leone. The study also concludes that an increase in the inflation rate will also lead to an increase in the ROA.

Finally, the result in table 3.2 shows that there is a weak and positive correlation that exists between Treasury bills rate and the Return on Assets ($r = 0.144730$, p. value = 0.7569). The result in table 3.3 further discovered that the T_BILLS_RATE have a negative coefficient value of -0.265647 with a p. Value of 0.0000 and statistically significant at a p. Value of 5% level. The null hypothesis in the study denotes that there is no significant relationship that exists between Treasury bill rates on the profitability of commercial banks. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that Treasury bill rate has a negative and significant effect on the profitability of

commercial banks. Implying that a unit increase in the Treasury bill rate will lead to a proportionate decrease in the ROA of the commercial banks.

5.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

The profitability of commercial banks is highly affected by changes in the monetary tools that are been used by the monetary authority. Since the operating environment of these commercial banks anchor on the policy that is been set by the monetary authority. The policy recommendations of the study are in line with the research findings in order to aid the smooth running of the commercial banks and hence increase their profitability which serves as their long term objectives. The policy recommendations of the study are as follows:

Firstly, the study recommends that policy makers should be cautious in changing the monetary policy rate as this rate will drives all other rate especially the interest rate and the inter-bank lending rates within the industry. A change in the monetary policy rate will drive changes in other rates thereby affecting the profitability of commercial banks either positively or negatively.

Furthermore, the study recommends that to ensure an efficient banking system that protect the interest of savers and the financial intermediaries, the reserve requirement has to be treated with caution as a more higher ratio, will limit the bank's chances of making profit and a lesser ratio, will stimulate excessive flow of funds into the economy which also has tendencies for inflation and other related macroeconomic issues.

Moreover, the study recommends that policy makers should ensure that necessary steps are taken to maintain the value of the Leone as compared to other foreign currencies as this will create the ease of facilitating trade finance by commercial banks at the lowest cost possible. Continuous increase in the general price level tends to benefits some sectors at the expense of others.

Also, the study recommends that rising cost of inflation has a positive and significant effect on bank's profitability but in the view of the researchers, rising inflation also often constraints bank's profitability. Therefore, policy makers must ensure that they maintain lower level of inflation to achieve a sound financial system that benefits the financial intermediaries, the surplus units and the deficit units.

Finally, the study recommends that the T-bills rate has a negative and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks, implying that the central bank should cautiously treat the T-bills rate as it has a direct effect to money transmission and hence influencing the profit potentials of commercial banks.

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